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A literature review about acculturation on the American Anthropologist: reduced version

Abstract

The research accomplished a literature review about acculturation on the earlier American Anthropologist journal. Acculturation research appeared on North American Anthropology; afterward it came to Sociology and Psychology. The main models to approach acculturation followed the historical evolution of the North American culture, and the earlier research barely considered the main dimensions of the acculturation concept. Assimilation and, in a lesser degree, fusion were the preferred models during colonial and imperial times, and American Indigenous were the main researched cultural group. Acculturation was approached as one-way of cultural influences, and (Indigenous) cultural change was the main concern. Yet, interaction and learning were not main concerns. The multicultural model appeared already in the earlier literature, yet it was related to fusion.

Keywords: Acculturation, fusion, multicultural, American Anthropologist.

Uma revisão da literatura acerca da aculturação ao American Anthropologist: versão reduzida

Resumo

A investigação realizou uma revisão de literatura acerca da aculturação na revista American Anthropologist. A investigação acerca da aculturação surgiu nos primórdios da Antropologia norte américa e, mais tarde, na Sociologia e na Psicologia. Os principais modelos da abordagem da aculturação seguiram a evolução histórica da cultura norte americana e a investigação inicial quase que não considerou as dimensões fundamentais do conceito da aculturação. Assimilação e, num grau menor, a fusão foram os modelos preferidos durante as épocas coloniais e imperiais, e os indígenas americanos foram o grupo cultural mais investigado. A aculturação foi abordada como tendo apenas uma direção de influências culturais, e as mudanças culturais nos indígenas constituíram-se como a problemática maior. Contudo, a interação e a aprendizagem não se constituíram como problemáticas fundamentais. O modelo multicultural já tinha surgido na literatura inicial. Contudo, nos artigos iniciais se relacionava com a fusão.

Palabras-chave: Aculturação, fusão, multicultural, American Anthropologist.

1. Acculturation definition and models

The research did a literature review about the acculturation concept on the earlier American Anthropologist journal. It was the first North American journal of Anthropology. It is the flagship journal of the American Anthropological Association, and it is still one of the most important journals at the global arena. The acculturation definition was important to limit the research scope. The acculturation phenomenon may be defined by its main dimensions, i.e., intercultural contact, mutual interactions among different cultures (Redfield, Linton & Herskovits, 1936), by learning a second culture (Powell, 1880; Rudmin, 2009), and by cultural changes at individual and collective levels.

Acculturation has four models; assimilation, multicultural, fusion and intercultural (Castro 2014a, b, 2015, 2016a, b, c, d, e, f; Castro & Rudmin, 2016). On the assimilation model the minority culture is expected to disappear. The mutual learning will not be reported on the expected outcome, because the minority will be assimilated. The Chicago School is an example of the model.

On the multicultural model, the minority culture is expected to get cultural adaptation, maintaining at the same time its own culture. On the multicultural approach, just the minority is described as learning, and both cultures are interacting with the larger society. The Berry Model (2001) is an example of the model.

On the fusion model, there is interaction, mutual learning among different cultures, and there are cultural mixtures, which will produce a new culture with inner diversity (Bastide, 1973; Castro, 2014a, b, 2015, 2016a; Herskovits, 1967; Frazier, 1942). The Freyre (1986/1933; Rudmin, Wang & Castro, 2016), and the Ortiz theories are examples of the fusion model. The intercultural model was not described in this work.

2. Empirical outcomes

On February, the 1, 2016, a refined search on the Website AnthroSource by the word acculturation gave 2162 outcomes on the American Anthropologist. The review codified 17 codes, and selected 90 earlier articles. The statistical outcomes found out that the main topic was cultural change (31.1%). Other relevant outcomes were

theoretical (10%), psychological traits (7.8%), review (5.6%), ethnic identity (6.7%), contact (5.6%) and health (5.6%). Other topics had three or less cases. On the 1950s acculturation research reached its maximum, because among 1951 and 1960 it had 42.2% of the outcomes. Most articles were written originally in English (96.7%). Authors were mostly North-Americans or they were working for universities placed in North America. They were mostly males (90%), and females were only 8.9%. The majority of articles were produced in USA or Canada (65.6%). Few works were produced about European countries, the exceptions were Netherlands by Baal in 1960, Denmark (Anderson, 1958) and Germany (Westphal-Hellbusch, 1959).

Anthropology was without surprise the main field (76.7%), followed by Psychology (17.8%), ‘The oldest of our recent trends, and the most important in terms of membership and number of publications, is Psychology’ (Meggers, 1946, p. 178). Meggers (1946) provided an extensive list of psychological references. Barnett et al. (1953) also reported the influence of Psychology. Sociology only got 2.2% of the outcomes. At methodological level measuring devices were employed (13.3%), and projective tests were employed on 10% of the articles.

A defining dimension of the acculturation concept is the direction, and mainly the two-way direction. The code options were one-way (66.7), two-way (28.9) and not defined (4.4). Hence, often just the minority was approached. Minority and majority cultural groups were described as active on 22.2% of the articles, yet they were not active in 47.8% of cases, and in 30.0% of cases were not defined. Cultures were described as interacting on 86.7% of the articles, and as not interacting on 7.8% cases, and it included also the not defined (5.6%) option. This code appeared, because there were few descriptions of interaction, and often just the minorities were described as learning the majority culture. Yet, interaction is a defining dimension of acculturation.

The main feature of the fusion model is to report a common and shared culture. Hence, one code was asking, ‘are cultural groups sharing cultural traits?’, and the outcomes were yes (26.7%), no (52.2%), and not defined (21.1%). Changes are also a defining dimension of the acculturation concept. However, the multicultural model is emphasizing the minority cultural maintenance and, at the same time, cultural adaptation. It reveals a contradiction, because adaptation also triggers changes. This code was asking; ‘is there mainly cultural change (4.4%) or maintenance (5.6%)’. Additional options were both of them (86.7), none (2.2%), and not defined (1.1%). The outcomes displayed that often cultural changes and maintenance were occurring at the same time, which reported the limits of the assimilation and multicultural models.

The next code was checked out taking into account the description of the relationship. The code asked, ‘is the relationship harmonious (6.7%), problematic (55.6%) or conflictual’ (20.0%). It also included the option not defined (17.8%). The outcomes confirmed that acculturation was often motivated and problematic. Another code

asked, ‘is there any asymmetric power relationship approached?’ The code outcomes were yes (50.0%), no (4.4%), and not defined (45.6%). The next code asked, ‘is discrimination approached?’, and unlike the previous two codes, it was not approached by the mere description of the relationship, because discrimination would be reported as a concern. The outcomes were yes (11.1%), no (11.1%) and not defined (77.8%). Hence, discrimination was not a main topic in the earlier anthropological research.

Indigenous was the most frequent minority label (45.6%), and Afro-Americans (2.2) often were not approached. Additional relevant outcomes were Eskimo (4.4%), more than two (11.1%), and not defined (16.7%). The statistical outcomes revealed the historical evolution of the acculturation concept and of the North American culture, because the West was still under colonization. Europeans were under acculturation only by Anderson (1958), and Willems (1944), and the latter approached Germans immigrants in Brazil. The majority labels and relevant outcomes were Anglo-American (27.8%), White (17.8%), Spanish (6.7%), more than two (7.8%), another (30.0%), and not defined (30.0%). The outcome on the not defined option (30%) reported that majorities were not under acculturation and that majorities were not a concern.

The review wanted to know which acculturation model was pervasive. The code options and outcomes were assimilation (31.1%), fusion (18.9%), multicultural (5.6%), and not defined (25.6%). Consequently, the assimilation model was pervasive, and it was followed by fusion. On the fusion model some of the works were theoretical, e.g., Hallowell (1957) criticized the pervasive one-way, and he provided other examples of fusionist works, i.e., Chamberlin, Foster, Beals and Gillin. The North-American Anglo-Saxon culture was rarely reported to learn second cultures and to produce mixed cultures, the exceptions were Merriam (1955), because he reported mixtures, for example, the jazz music, and Barnett in 1940.

The research did an additional search for the words plural and multicultural on the American Anthropologist database. The researcher downloaded the articles from the last pages of both searches in order to get the earlier articles. Most of the results were not connected with the multicultural model. The works of Vogt (1955) and Polgar (1960) were found during the search. Polgar (1960) provided more examples of multicultural works. He mentioned Bateson (1935), Tax (1941), Barnett et al. (1953), Bruner, 1956, and Crowley (1957). Yet, the work of Crowley (1957) was considered by the current review as fusionist, because he reported mixtures and shared cultures. Bateson (1935) did not write the word multicultural, but he provided clues about what was considered the plural society, ‘. . . the persistence of both groups in dynamic equilibrium within one major community.’ (Bateson, 1935, p. 74).

The common element among the descriptions of Tax (1941), Vogt (1955) and Polgar (1960) was that fusion was previous to the multicultural outcome. The three authors described in fact fusion processes. However, they ascribed them to the multicultural (plural) model, because there were cultural maintenances. Another common feature was that violence and asymmetric relationships occurred just during fusion. The multicultural outcome was described as peaceful by Tax (1941), Vogt (1955) and by Polgar (1960). Multiculturalism was called stable pluralism, because cultures were expected to be in permanent contact with relative tolerance (mutual recognition), and with no further cultural changes, which was not realistic.

Tax (1941) described Spaniards and Indigenous peoples in Guatemala. Spaniards, who were the dominant cultural group, changed and they became Ladinos, because they mixed with Indigenous. According to Tax (1941), the Indigenous culture achieved cultural maintenance, and they were described as an autonomous culture, regardless contact and intercultural relationship. It is interesting to notice that Tax explained the cultural maintenance, and the continuous intercultural contact with no change by Lamarck evolutionist thought. Consequently, the description of Tax was closer to the Herbert Spencer social evolutionism than to cultural relativism of Boas.

Vogt (1955) described Indigenous, Spanish-Americans and Anglo-Americans gathered together during Laguna Fiesta, New Mexico. Their relationships were characterized by economic motivations. Social roles were stables, and the different ethnic groups were interacting, but they were not described as changing. Fusion occurred between Spanish and Indigenous cultures, and it rendered to Spanish-Americans. In short, on Tax (1941), Vogt (1955) and Polgar (1960) the acculturation processes had only one-way, regardless that at least one culture was under fusion. Yet, the Anglo-Saxon culture was not described as learning any second culture.

3. Conclusions

The conclusion was outlined according to the acculturation defining dimensions, as they were provided at the outset, and considering culture as a dynamic process of fusion. The review outcomes reported that acculturation research went from Anthropology to Sociology and Psychology. On the anthropological literature acculturation research was a main topic from its earlier works until the 1960s. However, acculturation research appeared on colonial and imperial times. Europeans and Westerns were dominating the planet. Furthermore, eugenics, racism, and social evolutionist ideas appeared in order to vindicate European and Western domination and in some cases genocides. Hence, most works were reporting a problematic and asymmetric relationship, and discrimination topic just gained strength after the 1960s.

Cultural changes were the main topic of the anthropological literature, and the mere contact with intercultural interaction with two-ways of cultural influences was not a major concern. The outcomes reinforced the acculturation colonial and imperial backgrounds. Intercultural contact occurred among Westerns and American Natives, who were the main researched minority. Yet, Westerns were rarely reported as learning second cultures.

The reactions regarding the Western domination confirmed that acculturation was a motivated phenomenon, and that it was often asymmetric and antagonistic, because social dominance narratives were common, even when the minority cultural maintenance was a concern. The main questions were not the anthropological description of the Native culture and of the intercultural contact, but how to deal the asymmetric relationship or how to regulate the Western domination and exploitation.

Most of the authors were writing in English, and most of them were males working in North America. Later, the anthropological research was extended to South America, to Caribbean Islands and in a lesser degree to Africa and Asia. Psychology was a main field in the earlier anthropological literature, and it encompassed projective tests and measuring devices.

On further researches, the acculturation concept still needs to be contextualized. It is necessary to add additional social sciences to Anthropology, and the current review should be enlarged to the sociological and psychological literatures. The current review reported that Western majorities were not under acculturation, and that they were not a concern, even because often they were not supposed to change. However, today, in the USA the white majority will be a minority, and the white middle-class has often worse health (Case & Deaton, 2015) than first generations of immigrants, reinforcing the immigrant paradox (Markides & Coreil, 1986). Furthermore, the recent Western demographic changes (Case & Deaton, 2015) are leading to racism and to intercultural violence (Richeson & Sommers, 2016). Hence, it is necessary to approach Westerns and Europeans learning additional cultures.

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